

EXTRACTION FORM		QUALITY ASSESSMENT								SEARCH QUESTIONS						
Extraction Date	URL	Authority	Methodology	Objectivity	Date	Position	Novelty	Impact	Obs	Approved	How can White Label Startups be defined??	What are its characteristics?	What are the differences between White Label Startups and regular Startups?	Which SE methods are used by them?	Where the White Label name came from?	What are the challenges in White Label Software Projects?
10/1/2019	https://www.pedromasagem.com.br/home/convencionalidade/2017/05/20/white-label-startups-ua-estrutura-com-plataforma-de-estatisticas-para-afirma-e-alcanca-300-mil-downloads-em-3-meses.html	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES		YES	Desenvolver aplicativos de forma customizada para clientes	Criados sob demanda, podem conter funcionalidades especiais para cada cliente	no	no	no	no
10/1/2019	https://www.ivestor.com/launch-fintech-business	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	A Company's website that explains what is a white label software company	YES	The key principle of a white label business is simple: company A invests in development of a product (usually a complicated software), starts its own business in one region and then lets other companies from the same or other regions use their platform under their own label. Company B connects its own domain to A's software, but this process is invisible for the end clients. Company B clients come to B-brand and have no idea that all the backoffice operations are handled by company A.	no	no	no	no	no
10/1/2019	https://medium.com/startup-frontier/how-to-white-label-an-entire-company-2a6f1a2393b0	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	Medium post about white labeling a company	YES	White labelling is when a company uses an existing company's brand as a framework to develop their own conceptualisation. It allows that company to use an established product and not have the stress involved with focusing on developing their own brand from the ground up.	no	no	no	no	no
10/1/2019	https://medium.com/@DNAC93b0dd-you-are-white-label-epic-product-69766356543c	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES		YES	One of the best things I like about white label is that it lets you connect with agencies and other companies. This lets you grow your network and build relationships that help you a lot.	no	no	no	no	no
10/1/2019	https://www.aucora.com/What-startups-have-created-successful-white-label-products-and-services	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES		YES	Essa forma de desenvolvimento tem semelhanças com uma forma de trabalho terceirizada, já que a construção técnica fica por conta de outra organização. Existem vários motivos pelos quais a compra de softwares white label se tornou popular entre as empresas atuais, como benefícios financeiros e de qualidade. Entre os outros pros envolvendo o uso de plataformas white label estão: Menor custo de desenvolvimento – as plataformas são desenvolvidas sobre um código pré construído, que diminui o tempo e o esforço necessários para sua finalização. Não é necessário ter conhecimento de programação – toda a construção da inteligência é desenvolvida por terceiros. Menos investimento em uma equipe técnica – os empreendedores não precisam contratar profissionais dedicados ao desenvolvimento. Menor risco de implementação – com uma plataforma desenvolvida por profissionais, há menos problemas técnicos. Rapidez de inserção no mercado – com um tempo de desenvolvimento menor, as ideias podem sair do papel com mais rapidez.	no	no	no	no	no
12/10/2019	https://exame.abril.com.br/mecanismos/dono-plataforma-que-white-label-e-chave-do-sucesso-no-investimento-digital/	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO	Publicitary notice in a	YES	A ideia é simples: uma parceira de tecnologia desenvolve toda a estrutura e software digital, enquanto empresa financia sua personalização. Depois disso, com uma plataforma completa e funcional, os empreendedores podem cuidar do crescimento do negócio. Essa parece ser a ideia perfeita para centenas de startups que desejam se estabelecer no mercado atual.	A utilização de softwares white label começou na indústria musical, quando gravadoras ofereciam suas bases musicais para que DJs pudessem utilizar em suas mixagens. Na indústria digital atual, a ideia é bem parecida, já que a empresa que utiliza a plataforma finalizada não é a mesma que a desenvolveu.	no	no	no	no

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12/10/2019	https://www.thiscompany.com/white-label-marketing/what-is-white-label	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	A website that gives an ebook about white label products (MARKETING)	YES	A white label product is a product or service produced by one company that other companies rebrand to make it appear as if they had made it.				Its origins can be traced to vinyl records. Before records were to be released to the public, often before the official artwork was designed and printed, promotional copies were sent out in a white sleeve to DJs to solicit radio and nightclub play, in an effort to build hype and gauge public interest by the record labels, ultimately to better estimate manufacturing quantities. This created a situation where certain respected or well-connected DJs would have exclusive copies of material, immediately increasing demand on certain big records. Occasionally this term refers to records whose labels had been torn off or covered with a white label by competing DJs to conceal which records they were using.	
12/10/2019	https://webdium.com/blog/white-label-what-it-is-and-how-it-works-in-2019/	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO	White labeling is a type of partnership in which one company produces goods or services, and the other sells them under its own brand.	YES		Such an approach saves companies from the need to invest in creating their own technologies and infrastructure. Providers of white label products or services allow you to focus on product quality and increase your sales without investing in sales development. Marketers often compare white labeling with drop shipping. The company, that offers product or service, proposes you to buy them at a lower price than you will resell for the price you want. Note: you distribute these goods under your brand name, not under the producer's brand name. In other words, from that moment you are selling your own product!				
12/10/2019	https://northout.com/2018/04/white-labeling-what-is-white-labeling/	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO	A white-labeled product is something produced by one company and then sold under a brand name by somebody else. For example, "store brands" are almost always white-labeled products. A manufacturer with no consumer branding sells the product to the retailer, who can sell it for a higher price than the manufacturer due to their position in the marketplace.	YES					It's a great idea for startups to buy white label products and services for anything that isn't core to their business. It's a terrible idea, for the vast majority of startups, to try to start a white label business, or especially to pivot into one. Successful white label businesses have a reputation in the business community for providing consistent quality at a consistent price. The key word here is "consistency," not "quality" or "price." Most either focus 100% on building a white label business from square one, usually with quite a bit of existing capital, or build a reputation for themselves selling direct to consumer, then branch out or pivot into white-labeling after they've already found success.	

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12/10/2019	https://www.vendasta.com/blog/white-label-business-opportunities	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO		YES	<p>White-labeling is a business-to-business model involving manufacturers and resellers. Essentially, a software manufacturer sells an unbranded piece of software or a service to a reseller who then places their branding on the offering and resells it to their business clients. Digital products can be bought and sold over the net, so you generally require little (or zero) overhead to get started—all you've gotta do is start pounding the pavement and selling to businesses.</p>	<p>Advantages to the White-Label Business Model</p> <p>Here are some key product and service advantages that are driving the growth of white-label adoption among startups, agencies, and media groups around the world.</p> <p>Why resell white-label digital products?</p> <p>No physical distribution or need for brick and mortar stores Skip research & development and start selling instantly Local businesses need business and marketing tech to keep up with the big guys The fastest way to create or grow revenue</p> <p>Why resell white-label business services?</p> <p>White-label services build a stronger client relationship than simply a product offering Generate stable recurring revenue with ongoing services Minimal costs, risk, and staffing expenses with white-label service fulfillment Fast-tracked growth and easy scaling by leveraging fulfillment teams that grow with you Now you just have to decide which opportunity is the best fit for you</p>				
12/10/2019	https://www.fbdes.com/likes/likes/00140603/why-a-white-label-solution-is-greater-than-building-your-own/	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES		YES	<p>White-labeling is a business-to-business model involving manufacturers and resellers. Essentially, a software manufacturer sells an unbranded piece of software or a service to a reseller who then places their branding on the offering and resells it to their business clients. Digital products can be bought and sold over the net, so you generally require little (or zero) overhead to get started—all you've gotta do is start pounding the pavement and selling to businesses.</p> <p>It's quick and easy to brand. Saves you time and money. Developing a solution from scratch takes a large amount of financial and human capital resources — not to mention time. While a custom solution may seem at the outset to be the best alternative, you may quickly find that the effort derails internal business processes and blows budgets. Even if you think you can build it yourself, it's important to factor in time for marketing. Remember the time it takes for architecture, design, building, and testing the solution. If you require a fast deployment, cutting corners in any of these steps can leave you even further behind.</p> <p>When time is of the essence and you need to be speedy, investing in an existing solution may be more cost-effective in the end.</p> <p>It allows you to focus on your business's core competency. In many cases, the solutions that companies hope to build themselves fall far outside of their areas of expertise. It's not smart to stretch your resources to do something that doesn't fit within your core competencies. Be sure to look closely at the solution you need and compare it to your available resources to help you decide whether a white-label solution would help you reach your goals more efficiently. Prepackaged solutions provide an opportunity to trust the experts in the specific space you are focused on, and avoid making the same mistakes that others have made before you.</p> <p>In short, white-label solutions can help you utilize your business's unique branding to offer a product or service without investing in infrastructure or technology creation around the solution. The result: You can focus on building your brand and selling your services while simplifying the conversion path for your customers.</p>					
12/10/2019	https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/white_label_product	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES		YES	<p>White label production is often used for mass-produced generic products including electronics,[4] consumer products and software packages[5] such as DVD players, televisions, and web applications. Some companies maintain a sub-brand for their goods, for example the same model of DVD player may be sold by Dixons as a Sasho and by Currys as a Matsui, which are brands exclusively used by those companies.[6]</p> <p>Some websites use white labels to enable a successful brand to offer a service without having to invest in creating the technology and infrastructure itself. Many IT and modern marketing companies outsource or use white-label companies and services to provide specialist services without having to invest in developing their own product.</p>					
12/10/2019	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=AYmcClGgDg	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	VANDASTA I WILL TR	YES						

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12/10/2019	https://medium.com/@zangi/what-are-the-7-white-labeling-benefits-869e6331921a	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	ASK FOR INTERVIEW	YES	<p>First, let's find out what is white labeling. In simple words, a white label product is sold under one brand's name but created by another company. White labeling has become popular in recent years because not many companies have an in-house professional workforce to create messengers for their business from scratch. It is a faster solution which can save a lot of money and time.</p> <p>White labeling is used extensively by many companies. Zangi is the only company providing a white label solution to anyone who wants to create their own branded messenger with custom features and unique interface. A number of features can be added upon request.</p>	Characteristics already mentioned in other article				
12/10/2019	https://hubspot.com/2018/11/white-labeling-a-guide-to-successful-1782	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	It shows 7 types of wh	YES						

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												White labeling is a powerful strategy to increase your distribution. The white labeled solutions and products are very common because they require few resources from your partners and the implementation is much faster. You are able to build your own brand on white labeled products as well as create stronger relations with customers. White labeling may also boost your brand's visibility on the market. If you want to resell your vendor's offering you can set the price which is good for you. You can maximize your profits since you are in charge by bundle supporting. You can charge for the products as much as you want. By selling white labeled products, you can add value to them by mixing and matching the offerings of different vendors. It will customize your product line. Products are offered instantly. You can offer customers new quality products and services which means that you can react quickly to your competition to ensure you keep your customers and sustain their satisfaction. Obviously the third-party products that are white labeled by your company and added to your offering are dependable and satisfactory. When a client uses your white labeled product which is convenient and brings satisfaction, they will attach it to your brand's name, and have the same feelings about it. Designing a mobile app or a software is time consuming and requires a lot of knowledge. When you use white labeled product you can focus on promotion and selling of your main products which means you are getting closer to your goals. Creating your own mobile app from scratch might sound like a great idea at some point, but if you haven't done it successfully before, you have no idea how much energy and resources goes into creating an original product. A white labeled solutions allows you to get a software expertise and a product developed by a specialist in the related field. If the software or outsourcing developers have the knowledge and expertise to create a product better than you can do it, just pay them for the white labeling privilege and enjoy. White labelling reduces the commercial risk and allows you to test the market with a proven solution.													
12/10/2019	https://180creative.com/white-labeling-what-it-is-what-are-the-pros-and-cons-of-white-labeling	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES		YES	In simple words, a white label product is a products which is sold under one brand's name but was made by another company. In case of software development, services can be white-labeled too. Even though outsourcing is often white labeled, these two terms should not be used interchangeably. White label marketing is actually quite new concept on the market. It became popular during recent years. Marketing agencies used to struggle to provide a full package of marketing services to their clients. Being a full service marketing agency required having a large in-house trained workforce. Some companies are too small to provide all the services they would want to. This is the moment where white-labeling finds its place in the creation process. Helpful may it seem, it can cause trouble, too.						1)Misunderstandings. When you pass your vision and product description to the other software agency and they pass it on to their project manager at the development company who then passes the project to certain team. This stream of information may be distorted at some point. An important part of your vision and functionality of the product you want, may get lost along the way. The same thing may happen repeats with the feedback loop. The chances that your project's agenda will be changed and miscommunicated is a probable risk 2)The needs of users and clients go to the second plan. Understanding the vision of the product you require should be vital for the development team. You should have an access to the process of creation. Also the development team should be acknowledged with your business vision and market knowledge. 3)Over-the-budget pricing and deadline prolongation. Miscommunication may lead to huge delays in software development, unwanted functions and designs. You cannot risk losing money and time when the window of opportunity is so small. Your clients or users may be dissatisfied and go to your competition.								
12/10/2019	https://businesscollective.com/white-to-consider-before-white-labeling-your-app/index.html	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES		YES		3. White labeling may provide a good exit strategy.				2. White labeling may kill your future customer base.									
12/10/2019	https://www.quora.com/What-are-white-label-apps	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES		YES	Initial investment is less – Yes, the white label applications whether mobile or web does not require a ton of investment in the initial phase. And this can be beneficial for many companies including startups whose budget does not allow committing to a larger investment. Scope of Customization – With white label apps one can do plenty of customization to the app as per the brand's image. This comes handy when a client wants to completely sync a product or service in respect with its website and social media platforms etc. Minimized marketing time – Let's take an example of a regional taxi business already having a considerable fleet of vehicles/taxis. Now, this business already has its roots in the market so getting a white label app will be just as an additional feature for their customers. Maintenance after the release – The software companies that provide the white label apps such as ride-hailing applications also assure to provide support and maintained once the app is launched. This post-release maintenance is important if you may require updating the code or if an issue arises in the initial versions.						There are 2 ways that are widely known to build a white label service or product. One of them being by creating a multi-tenant app which means that the application instance will be same but each of the tenants will be getting an app with a bit different features set. In this, the model that is commonly used is SaaS (Software-as-a-service). The other way is by reusing the backend code but this requires changing the frontend of the app to give a unique appearance to the app so that it won't be an exact copy of the same app. In comparison, the multi-tenant approach is quite complex to build and further maintain.			For the purpose of convenience many white label services are now cloud-based and due to this client have to transfer the user's data to the cloud hence, letting the other company know their user's information. This can lead to the issue of vendor-locked solution which may further enhance data exportation troubles. In white label products & services, the clients do not have any control over the quality of the code that is used in creating the app of the software. Non-disclosure agreements have to be signed between both the parties stating their needs and requirements. So, the white label service provider will inform you about the code quality and client will have to trust their word for it. One of the main issues that come when dealing with the white label apps is facing the rejection when submission of the app is done in the app store. In white label apps, this rejection is quite possible as the application guidelines have also been modified in app stores to avoid clone and spam apps. Several times the white label app service providers only tend to include the mandatory set of features in the app but not the additional or trending features. These additional features if added can provide a great boost to the app in terms of reaching to a larger section of the audience. This leads to the limited in customization of the app features as the SaaS products do have a simple and basic number of features. The scalability of the white label app is the main problem that is faced because of the lack of updates of the applications. When it comes to developing a taxi app right from the scratch, then the company needs to ensure its working of the taxi application is smooth and efficient. In the case of white label apps, the client has no choice but to trust the decisions of the white label app provider which also includes their mistakes.					
12/10/2019	https://www.cloudways.com/blog/white-label-services-for-agency/	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	nothing new	YES															

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12/10/2019	https://www.sheneeb.com/blog/partner/white-labeling-co-branding/	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO		YES		Build your own brand By co-branding a vendor's products as your own, you are reinforcing your own branding and reputation. You also build a stronger relation with your customers. 2)Set your own margins You can set the price at which you want to resell the vendor's offering. 3)Maximize profits by bundling support Since you are in charge of supporting and customers, you can bundle support and charge as much as you want for support. 4)Add value by selling 3rd party products By selling white-labeled 3rd party products, you can mix & match the offerings of different vendors and optimize your product line. There are only three scenarios for me where white labeling makes sense: Pure white label – this is your business. Period. Necessity – you are bootstrapping, with no intention to sell your business, no investors to manage, so you're free to do whatever deals make sense (but remember the above caveat still apply). To take advantage of markets that you will never enter directly. If you will never enter the Chinese market as an example, then having a partner white label your software there may be ok. You will still have issues to deal with in terms of distraction, custom requests and exit complexities. If you're struggling to generate revenues for your startup, please consider these points before going down the white label path.			Can be challenging for start-ups/smaller organizations As a smaller/new company, it can be a little more challenging to position yourself as the vendor.2) Requires in-depth IT knowledge As the go-to resource for your customers, you need to be able to answer all their IT-related questions and issues.3)More resources required Being in charge of end-customer support typically requires having more resources.4)Time-consuming/slower on-boarding You need to build documentation like FAQs, marketing and training tools, etc.	
12/10/2019	https://www.startupco.co/2017/06/why-i-hate-white-labeling-for-startups/	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES		YES						Likelihood of generating real revenue: If you're a tiny startup with an unproven product and little cash in the bank, do you really think an established company is going to put their brand and reputation on the line and market your product? A layer between you and your users. When the customer or end user belongs to someone else it becomes really hard to make your product better. Will you get the feedback you need? Exit complexity: This is a big one for me as an investor. Again, excluding pure white label businesses, if you run white label as one part of your business, it can really mess things up when it comes time to sell your business. Your direct customer relationships are easy for a buyer to understand and may be in fact what they are buying you for.
12/10/2019	https://you.hubstaff.com/white-label-agency-expert-roundup/	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	This article explains about white label agencies. It adds lots of new information to the work, but we must analyse if can be added to the research	YES	White labeling is when a service produced by one agency is bran Throughout all of the experts' responses, I identified 4 themes for You need to establish a strong workflow It is vital to be transparent with your partner every step of the process Treat your client relationships like real partnerships and be in it for the long run Be laser-focused on what you do best Building a white label agency is by no means easy, and following around these principles, you are going to have the best chance for success.					1) Being able to share your experience: When you do great work as a traditional agency, you usually can add White label agencies need to function as part of their partner's team and to do that the agencies need to adapt The better your workflow, the more you can minimize this. 4) Finding ways to continue providing value: Those are the challenges you face while getting ramped up, but
12/10/2019	https://www.bankmobile.com/white-label	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	Large success story at	YES	Companies win in this model by: Reduced processing costs for on-partner purchases made with BankMobile accounts vs. other debit or credit cards. Earning revenue share from accounts. Gaining affinity from their customer base as accountholders are treated to customized rewards and perks. Customers win in this model by: Unique rewards and incentives. Access to virtually free checking accounts (and other financial services products) they may not have access to otherwise. Frictionless account opening with a brand that customers and employees are familiar with and trust.					
12/10/2019	https://amazonseconsultant.com/amazon-white-label-product/	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO	Article focused in white	YES	adds nothing new to the research					

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12/10/2019	https://www.oporbusiness.com/white-label-business-opportunities/	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO	With does say about white label business in general. But can be used to prove my opinion	YES		<p>How to Differentiate Your White Label Business</p> <p>When there are many competing products, you must differentiate your business so you don't get lost in the competition. Here are 4 ways that a white label reseller can stand out from the crowd.</p> <p>Differentiate like crazy! One way to do this by tightly defining your niche or by assembling several white label products together.</p> <p>Make sure your brand is readily apparent. Don't just put your logo in your ad. Include a tag line, a slogan or a one-line benefit statement about the product.</p> <p>Offer amazing customer service. Consumers today read online reviews before making purchases. If your customer service is fast, responsive and warm, word will spread and you will get positive reviews. Customer satisfaction will generate more sales.</p> <p>Use private label products as ancillary products to your main product line-up. Not AS your main line-up. That way, your private label products serve as up-sell opportunities for additional profit.</p>				
12/10/2019	https://uxdesign.cc/white-with-colour-815d9c9e-a-white-label-products.html#:~:q=white-label-products&hlq=815d9c9e37a3	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	White label Article for a specific problem	YES						
12/10/2019	https://startups.co.uk/the-white-labeling-business-model/	YES	NO	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	The white label business	YES	nothing new to add					
12/10/2019	https://blog.travelsayouts.com/en/how-to-create-a-white-label-website/	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	Is a website teaching	YES	<p>White Label allows you to rebrand a product or service so that it is identical to the original without having to create something from scratch or invest large amounts to make your product.</p> <p>There are many examples of companies – including Starbucks or, in technology, Dell – that use other manufacturers' White Labels and then apply their own brand to personalise and sell the product with greater credibility.</p> <p>However, be careful to not confuse White Label with the counterfeiting of a product.</p>					

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												<p>Having created a wide scope of white label software for clients, we have discovered a few learnings we'd like to share with you. In this checklist you will find some of the key points to bear in mind when planning your next project.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Customisation What do you really have in mind? 2. Features What are the must-haves? 3. Branding Are you competing with a recognised brand? 4. Value How will you add value? Look at combining complimentary packages into a bargain bundle or a two-for-one deal, where the customer will get the sensation that they are receiving excellent value for money. Always consider the end value for the customer, and how you can maximise that value in your software. 5. Partnerships How well do you know your developer? Always discuss the opportunity for partnerships with your software developer. Can you work together over a longer term, perhaps with support agreements or product development roadmaps? Your project is going to become a valuable asset to you, so ensure you can rely on them to stay on the journey with you as it evolves. 6. Development costs Do you know what the going rate is for software development? Be clear on what you expect to pay for the software you want. If the cost is over your planned budget, make sure you understand what the added benefit would be for spending more. Always aim to have an open conversation with the developer about cost – and potential discounts for multiple applications or longer term projects. 7. Integration How will the new software fit in? You should always have a defined strategy in place for building new software, and a clear view of how you expect it to impact the business. This is particularly important if the application needs to function alongside existing software, and share data with it. 8. Security Will the licensee worry about security issues? Always take the time to consider any potential security concerns the end user or licensee may have. How will the application be used, and what security risks will there be? What will the software be exposed to, and how can the application limit any security risks? 9. APIs How clear is the Application Programming Interface? Discuss the possibilities with your developer of how additional software integrations – if any – will be added. What APIs should be delivered with the initial product, and who's responsible for future integrations. 10. Support Who owns the support process? 					
12/10/2019	https://www.docsoftware.com/ultimate-white-label-development-checklist/	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES	White label Checklist	YES							
12/10/2019	https://www.redounge.com.au/blog/white-labeling-vs-co-branding/	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO	White label startup an	YES	White label software is, in its simplest form, an application that is produced by one business and marketed by another. Typically this marketer will act as a reseller, branding up the solution to appear to have been created by them. In most cases, the actual developers will produce the software at a fixed cost, while the reseller sets up subscription models or license agreements for the end user – often ensuring a substantial return on investment.						
											nothing new to add						

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												<p>There are some considerations when thinking about offering a white labeled product:</p> <p>If you want to build a large, start-up brand, white labeling is likely not the way to go, although co-branding works well (e.g. some pieces like the logo and colors of the app are customizable but the URL, documentation, etc refers to the core product name much like salesforce.com does)</p> <p>White labeling often works well if resellers are the primary distribution channel as well as having big companies resell it (in this case you're helping others build their brand and you're fine with being the behind-the-scenes provider)</p> <p>White labeling also works well if you offer an affordable product that goes on a credit card and brand doesn't play a role (e.g. Signalr.com and Campaign Monitor have great products that can be white labeled) in general, most startups that are considering a white labeled version of their product should start with a co-brandable version and see if that meets the market demand as most of the time it does.</p>				
12/10/2019	https://davidfourmings.org/2011/08/11/white-labeled-software-strategies-for-startups/	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES		YES						
12/10/2019	https://www.bullinchicago.org/2016/07/18/so-you-wanna-white-label	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES		YES	It displays more deeply in our area about the decision making when structuring a white label software					White labeling was originally a term used for when a musical artist would send out their new record in a white sleeve before album artwork was completed, hoping to garner hype and promotion in the clubs before the true release date. A more intuitive example would be a cereal manufacturer selling a generic box of corn flakes to Sam's Club and Target and letting each store brand the item themselves. That's why there is a real product out there named "Square Shaped Corn."
12/19/2019	http://www.sucra.com/What-startups-have-created-successful-white-label-products-and-services	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	YES	YES		YES	<p>One of the best things I like about white label is that it lets you connect with agencies and other companies. This lets you grow your network and build relationships that help you a lot.</p> <p>Running business gets a whole lot easier if you have the right connections and a network with appropriate people.</p> <p>With this in mind, startups should definitely stop up and offer white label services.</p>	<p>Not all startups prefer creating white label services. I have to say that it's a bold decision because you're, in a sense, letting others use your product with their own brand name (that's one form of competition).</p> <p>Not all startups like operating this way.</p> <p>I personally feel that startups should offer white label as it has more benefits than drawbacks.</p>				
12/19/2019	https://startuplawyer.com/startup-issues/white-label-is-the-way-black-for-startups	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	YES	NO		YES	<p>A white-label product or service is a product or service produced by one company (the startup) that another company rebrands for their own use or distribution. The company desiring to rebrand the startup's product or service may just want to overlay their custom skin on the startup's app. More frequently, the company will also request the development of new features for the white-label app.</p>	<p>The reseller obtains a possibility to quickly start-up in any market and to reduce its own costs in connection with the production process. In this case the reseller may focus on its primary business and earn additional profit from the partnership program without investing huge amounts of money in developing new and complementary products. However, the reseller may not interrupt and influence the manufacturing process as all the technologies and design are part of the manufacturer's sphere of responsibility.</p> <p>The manufacturer may sell its own products and services without paying additional costs with respect to advertising and promoting its products. Moreover, the option of the White Label Agreement allows the manufacturer to expand the range of customers of its goods and services, to form a successful business model to offer to the other potential similar partners. As disadvantages for the manufacturer we may indicate that recognition of products brings benefit not for its own goodwill and business reputation but for the reseller's goodwill and reputation. In addition, there are difficulties in getting direct feedback from customers with respect to its products as all the contacts with the customers are maintained through the reseller.</p> <p>Another important aspect is selling its goods and services to the reseller for a lower price in comparison with the situation where it would sell it independently.</p>	<p>The parties to the White Label Agreement shall regulate the following aspects:</p> <p>Whether the manufacturer is allowed to communicate directly to customers of its goods and services (typically not allowed);</p> <p>Whether your contracts provides exclusivity for parties (for instance, the manufacturer may be restricted in its right to resell products within a particular geographic region or within a specified period of time to other resellers or under your own name);</p> <p>Whether the making of product changes or modifications is allowed;</p> <p>Which performance progress is required from the parties in the first year and in all subsequent years;</p> <p>How the costs and expenses should be split between the parties (for instance, who shall pay the cost of marketing materials, freight and transport costs, taxes and duties, etc.);</p> <p>Whether the manufacturer retains ownership to the product recipe or formulation and the reseller – all intellectual property rights;</p> <p>Whether the products comply with valid quality standards;</p> <p>Who bears product liability;</p> <p>Which amount of products and services will be supplied by the manufacturer for its reselling by the reseller, etc.</p>			
12/19/2019	https://www.aacslaw.com/white-label-agreement-in-simple-terms/	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO		YES	The White Label concept is understood as a concept that involves the production of goods or services by one company and the use of these goods and services by another company under its own brand. The White Label strategy is widely used in the production of electronics, foods, software, etc.					

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12/10/2019	https://www.ett.com/news/features-and-news/behind-new-white-label-label-14546									NOT RELATED						
12/10/2019	https://www.aubusson.com/blog/white-label-brand-jean/									NOT RELATED						
12/10/2019	https://www.aubusson.com/white-label-video-production									NOT RELATED						
12/10/2019	https://www.myjackussell.it/free-white-label-software.html									NOT RELATED						
12/10/2019	https://the-mbianchirook.it/white-label-digital-wallet-india.html									NOT RELATED						
12/10/2019	http://manigraphics.com/white-label-reseller-business-opportunities.html									NOT RELATED						
12/10/2019	https://www.cmc.com/news/working30083207/cisco-mounting-white-label-market-offensive-aimed-at-driving-recurring-revenues.htm									NOT RELATED						
12/10/2019	https://mto.levelivety.it/white-label-software-business-model.html									NOT RELATED						
12/10/2019	https://mto.levelivety.it/white-label-software-business-model.html									NOT RELATED						
12/10/2019	https://myfruckpulse.com/									NOT RELATED						
12/10/2019	https://www.fawaz.com/white-label.php									NOT RELATED						
12/10/2019	https://www.info.maestro.it/									NOT RELATED						
12/10/2019	https://ufw.ghymla.it/white-label-sayment-gateway-prices.html									NOT RELATED						
12/10/2019	https://www.cnbc.com/2019/11/04/goldman-leads-50-million-investment-in-credit-card-start-up-deceive.html									NOT RELATED						
12/10/2019	http://mrx.it/white-label-sayment-gateway-prices.html									NOT RELATED						
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12/19/2019	https://www.demandgenreport.com/features/demanding-white-label-startup-maas-impact-into-marketing-as-service-white-label									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://bravenews.com/insights/bitcoin-startup-bitnet-partners-with-white-label-payments-solution-pay-ai									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://quest.com/companies/white-label-fox									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://www.white-labels.com/									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://www.forbrnwriting.com/best-white-label-free-gating-idea/									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://smallbiztrends.com/2018/11/white-label-app-business.html									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://www.fundRazr.com/blog/white-label-crowdfunding-software-at-your-next-startup/									NOT RELATED						
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12/19/2019	https://crowdfunder.com/white-label-crowdfunding-platform-idea-ideas-ideas/									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://jungleworks.com/white-label-app-development/									NOT RELATED						
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12/19/2019	https://www.techcrunch.com/2019/12/19/straight-line-ad-analytics-admission-startup-reduce-data-launches-white-label-platform-for-agencies/									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://www.ecommerce360.com/white-label-products/									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://finder.ai/motioncentral-ai-company-opens-world-class-ai									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://white-label-fox.com/									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://lbbadit.com/blog/white-label-app-development-101/									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://www.insideanalytics.com/mkt-105-white-label/									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://www.shipbob.com/startup-fulfillment-services/									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://maxirect.com/blog/white-label-companies/									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://www.smartdataso.com/services/white-label-lead/									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://kkesdpo.com/									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://www.ocilion.com/en/white-label-igyc-service.html									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://www.phocuswire.com/startup-pilch-tickets-launch-450k-raised-for-white-label-distribution-of-event-tickets									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://stackoverflow.com/questions/32653782/compl-on-startup-white-label-error									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://www.wowtechhub.com/business/5-reasons-why-a-startup-should-consider-white-label-solution/									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://ig.nips.yahoo.com/startup-white-label-whatsapp-lead-generation-build-own-100903472.html									NOT RELATED						

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12/19/2019	https://www.cobc.com/2019/11/04/goldman-leads-50-million-investment-in-credit-card-start-up-deavena.html									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	http://www.ornadagency.com/telemarketing-companies-consider-outourcing-for-white-label-reseller/									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://startupeurope.net/startup?id=1517									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://www.shiftoom.com/blog/white-label-brand-test/									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	http://www.cdn1118belxpo.co.uk/theatre/amazon-startup-workshop									NOT RELATED						
12/19/2019	https://www.cdn1118belxpo.co.uk/theatre/amazon-startup-workshop									NOT RELATED						
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10/1/2019	https://bundi.com/blog/intrapreneurship-4-studio-startup-factory-white-label-existing-corporate-assets	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	It is a video explaining how to white label internal projects in a large company to resell to the market	NO						
10/1/2019	https://codounderlab.com/issuunder-what-conditions-should-a-startup-white-label-their-product	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	YES	It is a founder's forum, this post highlights business questions about white labeling a startup product	NO						
10/1/2019	https://www.startups.com/community/question/4956-is-it-better-to-white-label-an-existing-business-or-development-of-develop-new-one	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO		NO						
10/1/2019	https://revistapegn.globe.com/Noticias/indical/2011/4/07/startup-cra-entre-digital-para-hebeseu-24una-c-100-mil-por-mes.html	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO		NO						
10/1/2019	https://www.whitelabelxpo.co.uk/masterclass/startup-masterclass/	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	White label conference	NO						
10/1/2019	https://www.tripsolver.net/white-label-travel-portal/	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	White Label business	NO						
10/1/2019	https://www.startuprad.io/blog/creators-collective-offers-a-white-label-service-for-product-development	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	Podcast aiming to explore	NO						
10/1/2019	https://www.modgimarketing.com/white-label-marketing-startup-agency/	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	Not startup or software	NO						
10/1/2019	https://www.mipsa.com/newsroom_item_page/Developer-un-business-ou-startup-empire-one-solution-participative-marque	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	Website error on open	NO						
10/1/2019	https://thebunch.com/2013/11/18/believe-in-white-label/	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	White label company	NO						
10/1/2019	https://icabstartup.com/	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	White label company	NO						
10/1/2019	https://www.e-startup.com/2019/07/19qa-based-e-scooter-startup-also-introduces-new-white-label-solution-that-allows-anyone-to-launch-a-ride-sharing-service/	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO		NO						

EXTRACTION FORM		QUALITY ASSESSMENT									SEARCH QUESTIONS					
Extraction Date	URL	Authority	Methodology	Objectivity	Date	Position	Novelty	Impact	Obs	Approved	How can White Label Startups be defined??	What are its characteristics?	What are the differences between White Label Startups and regular Startups?	Which SE methods are used by them?	Where the White Label name came from?	What are the challenges in White Label Software Projects?
12/10/2019	https://www.nameshops.com/startupwebsites/testing-seller-white-label/	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	White label reselling v	NO						
12/10/2019	https://www.99designs.com/7-facts-no-body-kids-you-know-white-label-digital-marketing-services/	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	Marketing white label	NO						
12/10/2019	https://spon.com/blog/programmatic-5-key-differences-between-white-label-vs-self-served-DSP/	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	Marketing white label	NO						
12/10/2019	https://www.wordpress.com/blog/2019/05/09/white-label-tips/	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	Marketing white label	NO						
12/10/2019	https://www.smartinsights.com/digital-marketing-strategy/white-label-revenue-models-white-labeling-5-tips-to-avoid-common-pitfalls/	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	Marketing white label	NO						
12/10/2019	https://www.aceperhead.com/blog/2018/04/18/its-down-your-best-best/	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO		NO						
12/10/2019	https://ticketflipping.com/blog/white-label-guide-strategy/	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	Article for market a wh	NO						
12/10/2019	https://www.efrasoft.com/white-label-trading-software/	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	Article about white lab	NO						
12/10/2019	https://www.zhouzouwa.com/Why-the-white-label-option-is-key-for-travel-startups/	NO	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES		NO						
12/10/2019	https://www.dacast.com/blog/how-does-white-label-video-streaming-work/	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	Article covering white	NO						
12/10/2019	https://www.reuters.com/article/white-label-franchise-managers-jump-into-the-ai-market/idUSL2N0M712M20140424/	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO		NO						
12/10/2019	https://searchides.com/white-label-ace-seller-program/	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO		NO						
12/10/2019	https://www.99designs.com/white-label-ace-seller-program/	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	White Label Marketing	NO						
12/10/2019	https://mytaxipulse.com/	YES	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	NO	A white label app	NO						
12/19/2019	https://www.startups.com/community/question/44956/in-the-white-label-an-existing-saas-in-development-or-developer-to-cow/	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES		NO						
12/19/2019	https://comunidad.iafba.com/esp/entrepreneur/2019/07/19/qa-based-e-seller-startup-ajm/	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES		NO						
12/19/2019	https://www.eu-startups.com/2019/07/19/qa-based-e-seller-startup-ajm/	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES	adds nothing new	NO						
12/19/2019	https://officechall.com/startups/2019/07/19/qa-based-e-seller-startup-ajm/	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO		NO						
12/19/2019	https://www.aceperhead.com/blog/white-label-ace-seller-program/	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO		NO						
12/19/2019	https://www.aceperhead.com/blog/white-label-ace-seller-program/	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO		NO						
12/19/2019	https://www.aceperhead.com/blog/white-label-ace-seller-program/	NO	YES	NO	YES	NO	NO	NO		NO						
12/19/2019	https://www.aceperhead.com/blog/white-label-ace-seller-program/	YES	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	NO		NO						
12/19/2019	https://www.aceperhead.com/blog/white-label-ace-seller-program/	YES	NO	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES		NO						
12/19/2019	https://www.resultesting.com/white-label-brand-testing-1-5-million/	YES	YES	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	Article invalidated bec	NO						
12/19/2019	https://www.startupdaily.net/2019/04/comparison-ace-seller-cma/	YES	NO	NO	YES	NO	NO	YES		NO						